

Synthesis of *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones^ψ

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N'-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesised by the reaction of 2-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate with salicylic acid hydrazine.

Pyrazoles and pyrazolin-5-ones represent important classes of heterocyclic compounds possessing wide range of biological activities¹. Incorporation of hydrazono²/azo³ group enhances the biological activity of heterocycles. Carboxylic acid hydrazides⁴ are generally used as antibacterial agents.

2-pyrazolin-5-ones.

The diazotised aromatic amines when condensed with reactive methylene position of β -ketoester, give 2-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (1a-i). The latter on cyclisation with salicylic acid hydrazine give *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2a-i) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Hence, it was considered worthwhile to prepare *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian spectrometer (270 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard.

N'-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (2a-i): The starting substituted primary amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (5 ml) and water (8 ml) was cooled to 0°. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was then added to it and the diazonium salt so formed was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (8 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The resulting solids were washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid to furnish 1a-i (65–75%): **1a**, m.p. 184° (Found: C, 62.15; H, 5.68; N, 11.47. C₁₂H₁₄N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 61.53; H, 5.98; N, 11.96%); ν_{\max} 3450 (NH), 2910 (CH), 1690 (C=O), 1520 cm⁻¹ (NH-N=C); δ 1.40 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.73 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 7.10–8.05 (m, ArH), 9.85 (1H, s, NH); **b**, m.p. 65–66°; **c**, 178–79°; **d**, 195–96°; **e**, 119–20°; **f**, 45–46°; **g**, 125–26°; **h**, 90–91°; **i**, 89°.

A mixture of 2-hydroxybenzoylhydrazine (0.001 mol) and 2-(substituted-phenylhydrazono)ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (1a-i; 0.001 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid was heated over a water-bath for 6 h. The solids that separated on cooling were dried and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield 2a-c (60–65%): **2a**, m.p. 254° (Found: C, 62.75; H, 4.13; N, 17.58. C₁₇H₁₄N₄O₃ calcd. for: C, 63.35; H, 4.34; N, 17.39%); ν_{\max} 3280 (NH), 2950 (CH), 1670 (C=O cyclic), 1560 (heterocyclic five-membered ring),

^ψPresented in the Sixteenth Conference of Indian Council of Chemists, held at Mangalore University, Magalagangothri.

Note

1510 (NH) and 750 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); δ 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.85 (1H, s, OH), 7.10–8.20 (8H, m, ArH) and 9.45 (1H, br, NH); **b**, m.p. 295°; **c**, 304°; **d**, 250°; **e**, 210°; **f**, 230°; **g**, 215°; **h**, 198°; **i**, 260°.

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